

Devyāmata, mūlapādapīṭhalakṣaṇapañcāśītipāṭalaḥ, edition.

N f89r, line 5; Mf64v, line 4; W, after a missing portion that commences in chapter 84, resumes the record at 85.14 on f71v, line 6

- 85.1 atah param pravakṣyāmi mūlapādasya lakṣaṇam
śīlānyāsaṃ purā kṛtvā kuryāc chilatalaṃ samam
- 85.2 prāsādavistaraṃ bhadre jagatīrathakānvitam
prāgrīvamaṇḍapopetaṃ madhyasūtrasusammitam
- 85.3 dhārākarnasamaṃ kṛtvā sarvasūtrasamaṃ talam
śīlābhir iṣṭakābhir vā mūlapādaṃ cinet sudhīḥ
- 85.4 ekaṃ dhārasamaṃ sarvamūlapādaṃ niranteram
ekaikasmimś caye kuryāt susthiraṃ sandhivarjitam
- 85.5 tāvad eva cinet vidvān yāvat syād bhūtalasamam
mūlapādasamaṃ kṛtvā pīṭhabandhaṃ samārabhet
- 85.6 śailaje śailajaṃ pīṭhaṃ mūlapāde tu śailaje
aiṣṭaje ceṣṭajaṃ samyak pīṭham āyatanasya tu
- 85.7 sūtradhārāsamaṃ kṛtvā mūlapādasamaṃ tataḥ
pūrvavat madhyasūtreṇa prāsādaṃ parikalpayet
- 85.8 pūrvamatsyadvayenaiva diksūtraṃ samprasādhayet
prāsādāvayavān paścāt tena sūtreṇa sādhayet

Mf65r

N f89v

Ω = NM(→W)

N lacks verses 2-5b.

W records chapter 85 from 14a onward.

1d kuryāc] N; ryāc M • samam] M; sama N 2c prāgrīva] em.; prāgīva M
• maṇḍapopetaṃ] em.; maṇḍapopeta M 3d cinet] em.; cit M • sudhīḥ] em.; sudhī M
4b mūlapādaṃ] em.; mūlapāda M 4c ekaikasmimś caye] em.; ekaikasmimścaye M
• kuryāt] em.; cakuryā M 5a eva] em.; evāñ M • cinet] em.; cine M
5b tala] em.; talam M 5d bandhaṃ] N; bandha M
6b śailaje] N; śailajet M 6c ceṣṭajaṃ] N; caiṣṭaje M • samyak] N; śastaṃ M
7a dhārāsamaṃ] M; dhārāmsamām N 8b sūtraṃ] N; sūsūtraṃ M
8c prāsāsāvayavān] em.; prāsādāvayavām N; prāsādāvayavā M 8d tena] N; reṇa M

- 85.9 jagatīrathakopetaṃ prāgrīvamaṇḍapānvitam
sudṛḍhaṃ susamaṃ kṛtvā mūlapādaṃ susammitam
- 85.10 kṛtvā dhārāsamaṃ sarvaṃ sutalaṃ karṇasammitam
pūrvavat sūtramārgeṇa pīṭhabandhaṃ tu kārayet
- 85.11 prāsādasya svamānena pīṭhasyaivocchrayeṇa tu
uttamādikrameṇaiva pīṭhasya lakṣaṇaṃ śṛṇu
- 85.12 caturaśrasya vṛttasya aṣṭāśrasya svanāmataḥ
caturaśrāyatasyaiva tathā vṛttāyatasya ca
- 85.13 prāsādānāṃ tu sarveṣāṃ svamānavistareṇa tu
trividhaṃ pīṭhaṃ evātra procyate śṛṇu sāmpratam
- 85.14 ucchrayeṇottamaṃ pīṭhaṃ prāsādārdhena kīrtitam
madhyamaṃ pādahīnaṃ syād uttamārdhena kanyasam
- 85.15 brahmaṇaś cottamaṃ pīṭhaṃ viṣṇoś caiveśvarasya tu
īśvarasya yathākāmaṃ anyeṣāṃ caiva kanyasam
- 85.16 evaṃ pīṭhocchrayaṃ jñātvā prāsādasya svamānataḥ
tataḥ saṃcinayet pīṭhaṃ jagatīrathakānvitam

Mf65v; Wf72r

$$\Omega = NM(\rightarrow W)$$

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|---|---------------------------------------|
| 9b maṇḍapānvitam] M; maṇḍapānvitām N | 10a sarvaṃ] N; sarvva M |
| 10d bandhaṃ] N; bandhadhan M | 11d śṛṇu] N; śṛṇuḥ M |
| 12a vṛttasya] M; vṛttasyavṛttasya N | 12b aṣṭāśrasya] N; aṣṭāmśrasya M |
| 13a sarveṣāṃ] N; sarvveṣā M | 13b māna] N; nāma M |
| 14a ucchrayeṇottamaṃ] em.; utsrayeṇottamaṃ NM | |
| 14b prāsādārdhena] N; prāsārdhena M | 14c hīnaṃ] N; hīna M |
| 16c pīṭhaṃ] N; pīṭha M | 16d rathakānvitam] N; rathakānvitām M |

- 85.17 ekaikasya caye pīṭhaṃ cined dhārāsamaṃ budhaḥ
evaṃ susaṃcitaṃ kṛtvā dvitiyaṃ cayam ārābhet
- 85.18 brahmabhāgapraveśaṃ ca tathā brahmaśilocchrayam
pīṭhasamucchrayaṃ samyag adhaś cordhvaṃ vikalpayet
- 85.19 kūrmaśilocchrayaṃ caiva tathā śvabhrasamucchrayam
vikalpya bahudhā bhādre madhye kūrmaśilām nyaset
- 85.20 praveśabrahmabhāgasya jñātvā brahmaśilocchrayam
tyāgabhāgaṃ parityajya garbhe tām saṃniveśayet
- 85.21 yathā brahmaśilā madhye tasya madhye tu tiṣṭhati
tathā tām vinyased yatnāt samyak kūrmaśilopari
- 85.22 niścalā sutalā kṛtvā śilā ca lakṣañānvitā
pīṭhaśilām kramaṃ kuryāt tatra madhye prakalpayet
- 85.23 pīṭhabandhaṃ tataḥ kuryāt samyak piṇḍocchrayānvitam Wf72v
caturaśraṃ tataḥ śvabhraṃ paridhikarṇasammitam
- 85.24 evaṃ śvabhrānvitam pīṭhaṃ kṛtvā vai sutalaṃ samam Mf66r
pīṭhasyordhvaṃ tato yatnād diksūtraṃ samprasārayet
- 85.25 mūlapādaḥ samākhyātaḥ pīṭhabandhasamanānvitam
pīṭhordhvaṃ procyate bhādre brahmasūtrasya lakṣañām
iti mūlapādapīṭhalakṣañāpañcāśītipaṭālaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

N is illegible, due to folio damage at 21c-22b and 25c to the end of the chapter.
title.

- 17a caye] M; cayet N 17b dhārā] em.; dhāra NM 17d cayam] N; camam M
18d adhaś] N; [[at]]adhaś M 19a śilocchrayaṃ] N; śilocchrayaś M 19d śilām] N; śilā M
20a praveśa] N; praveśā M 21ab brahmaśilāmadhye tasya madhye] M; brahmaśilāmadhye N
21d yatnāt] em.; yannā M • kūrma] em.; karma M 22a niścalā] em.; viśvalā M
22b śilā] em.; śilās M • lakṣañānvitā] em.; lakṣañānvitāḥ M; [****]tā N 22c śilām] N; śilā M
22cd kuryāt tatra] em.; kuryācchatra NM 23a bandhaṃ] em.; bandhan N; bandha M
23b piṇḍocchrayānvitam] em.; piṇḍocchrayānvitam N; pīṭhocchrayānvitam M 23c tataḥ] M; tata N
24c pīṭhasyordhvaṃ] em.; pīṭhasyorddhvaṃ N; pīṭhasyorddhva M • yatnād] em.; yatnā NM
25a pādaḥ] N; pādas M